

**FATIGUE DAMAGE MODELLING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
FROM BENDING TESTS**

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ABSTRACT

A fatigue damage model for unidirectional composite materials loaded in the fiber direction is proposed and identified from three-points bending tests. This model uses one local damage variable D which is defined from the local stiffness loss and for which a simple evolution is assumed, introducing three material constants to be identified from experiments.

Since bending tests result in non uniform stress and damage distributions, this identification requires a structural analysis which is here performed along a simplified line using Navier-Bernoulli's assumption. A general identification procedure is then presented taking into account some kind of statistical dispersion for the material constants. The corresponding results are presented on a glass epoxy composite.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue damage in composite materials is often characterized through the loss of rigidity [1] and, in particular, this seems quite appropriate in case of unidirectional composites loaded in the fiber direction. In many cases this is realized in three-points or four-points bending tests under prescribed load or displacement. The observed rigidity loss however cannot be precisely interpreted since it results from the integration of non-uniform damage over the whole structure

Damage mechanics on the other hand [2] provides a powerful approach for lifetime predictions in engineering structures. The degradation of the material is considered in the form of a damage internal variable D , as part of the rheological description of the material. The purpose of the present work is to use this kind of model for the interpretation of bending fatigue tests and to derive from them a local damage model to be used in more complex structures (finite elements for example).

LOCAL DAMAGE MODEL

An unidirectional model of elastic damage is considered. The damage variable is defined from the local rigidity by

$$(1) \quad \sigma = E(D) \cdot \epsilon \quad ; \quad E(D) = E_0 \cdot (1-D)$$

and a fatigue evolution law is postulated giving the damage increment per cycle dD/dN as a function of the present damage value and of the applied cyclic loading (amplitude $\Delta \epsilon$, ...). For instance, the following form has been used

$$(2) \quad dD/dN = \begin{cases} A (\Delta \epsilon)^c / (1-D)^b & \text{in traction} \\ 0 & \text{in compression} \end{cases}$$

with three material constants A , b and c to be identified from experiments. However since these experiments are realized in a non homogeneous situation, this identification requires coupling with a structural analysis.

APPLICATION TO BENDING FATIGUE

This structural analysis has been performed for a three-points bending test [3] on a rectangular specimen (length l , width b , thickness h , Figure 1). In a strength of materials approach, this proceeds in two stages.

Figure 1

At the first level, the bending behaviour is characterized under prescribed bending moment m or curvature χ : for a given damage distribution $D(y)$, the stress $\sigma(y)$ is obtained by substituting Navier-Bernoulli's assumption, $\epsilon = \chi(y - y_0)$, in (1). The position of the neutral fiber y_0 and the bending stiffness $H = m/\chi$ then result from integration on the beam thickness h .

$$(3) \quad y_0 \cdot \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(y)] \cdot dy = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(y)] \cdot y \cdot dy$$

$$(4) \quad H = m/\chi = b \cdot E_0 \cdot \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(y)] \cdot y \cdot dy$$

The evolution of the damage at each y , and therefore of y_0 and H is then obtained from the integration of (2).

At the second level the three-points bending test is analysed under prescribed load P or displacement δ : the problem is isostatic and the bending moment m is known in each section x , so that the results of the first step can be used. The global stiffness $k = P/\delta$ then results from Castigliano's theorem

$$(5) \quad 1/k = \delta/P = 2 \int_0^{l/2} \frac{(l/2 - x)^2}{H(x)} dx$$

These integrations are performed on a 10×40 mesh and Figure 2 shows a typical evolution of the stress and damage distributions in the central section ($x=0$) of the specimen under prescribed load amplitude ($b=8$, $c=2$, the final stage resulting in a global stiffness reduction of 58%: $k=0.42k_0$). The displacement of the neutral fiber and the apparition of a complete damage on the surface of the specimen can be observed.

Figure 2

It also follows from these computations that, as long as the usual conditions are considered, there is not so much difference between the tests performed at fixed load or displacement amplitudes: about 1% difference for a stiffness reduction of 10%.

IDENTIFICATION PROCEDURE

The material constants introduced in the model should be identified by comparison of the previously described results with experiments. The necessary experimental results consist in the evolution of the rigidity k as a function of N for different load or displacement amplitude levels. Practically the global rigidity ratio $k(N)/k_0$ is determined by following the displacement amplitude $\Delta\delta$ for a fixed load amplitude ΔP_0 or vice versa.

In the investigated special case (2), the three dimensionless material constants A , b and c are to be determined. The constant A may be considered as a scale factor for the number of cycles N . For a given value of b and c , a master curve is obtained for the rigidity $k(N)/k_0$ as a function of $X = AN$. A least square approximation can then be used to choose the best value of A to fit a given $k(N)/k_0$ -curve.

As for the determination of the two remaining constants, mathematical optimization techniques cannot be used and a qualitative procedure has been used. The b constant controls the self acceleration of the degradation process and thus the curvature and shape of the master curve $k(X)$. Its value will therefore be chosen to fit this shape at a given level.

This is illustrated in Figure 3 which shows the dependence of a normalized master curve (X_{90} represents the value of $X = AN$ corresponding to a stiffness reduction of 10%, $k/k_0 = 0.9$) on b at fixed $c=2$. Comparison of these curves with experiments allows the determination of b .

Figure 3

The c constant controls the non linear amplitude dependence and the slope of the Wöhler curve which gives the number of cycles N_{90} for a stiffness reduction of 10% as a function of the applied load or equivalently of the initial maximum stress S . An example is given on Figure 4 for $b = 5$.

Figure 4

STATISTICAL ASPECTS

Such a deterministic identification however cannot account for the dispersion which is essential feature of damage in composite materials. A reasonable damage model for composite materials must therefore include this statistical aspect from beginning. Our basic assumption will be that the only material constant concerned by the statistical distribution for A.

The identification procedure is the following.

1. For a fixed value of b and c, a least square approximation gives for each experimental curve an optimum value of A and an evaluation of the corresponding error.

2. For a fixed value of c, an optimum value of b can be obtained by minimizing a mean-value of this error over all available experimental results.

3. For a fixed value of b, an optimum value of c can be obtained by comparing the statistical distribution obtained for A at different levels and by minimizing the differences between them.

Starting from a given set of experimental results, a few iteration on steps 2 and 3 will provide the values of the material constants b and c. The statistical distribution of A will then be derived from step 1.

RESULTS

This identification procedure has been applied to the results obtained by P. De Roo and B. Paluch [4] on glass-epoxy unidirectional composites under fixed load amplitudes. Three amplitude levels (S=500, 600 and 700 M.Pa) were tested and

Figure 5

the experimental data were analysed for 10 identical specimens ($l=160$ mm, $b=30$ mm, $h=8$ mm) at each level.

The optimum values of the material constants have been found as $b=1.50$ and $c=5.40$. Two examples of experimental curves are given in Figure 5 with their identification. The resulting distribution for A is represented in Figure 6.

Figure 6

CONCLUSION

Fatigue bending tests can be used quantitatively to construct and identify a complete unidirectional damage model to be used in more complex situations. Though in a very simple way, this model includes a statistical dispersion. This statistical approach however assumes that each specimen is materially homogeneous.

It can therefore account for the dispersion resulting from preparation conditions but not for the material dispersion inside a specimen. In particular, it cannot explain the size effects which are observed [4]. A more refined approach accounting for material inhomogeneity can be developed along the same line.

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